

NFDI4Microbiota

National Research Data Infrastructure for Microbiota Research

2nd NFDI4Microbiota Community Workshop, 2020-03-11, Leipzig

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Plan for this session

Introduction to NFDI

Introduction to NFDI4Microbiota

Feedback

RFII

- Council for Scientific Information Infrastructure (Rat für Informationsinfrastrukturen, RfII)
- Implemented in 2014 by the Joint Science Conference (Gemeinsame Wissenschaftskonferenz, GWK)
- A council with advisory function: Recommendation on systemic level, no implementation on operational level

ENHANCING RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT: PERFORMANCE THROUGH DIVERSITY

Recommendations regarding structures, processes, and financing
for research data management in Germany

Recommendations of the RfII

- Building of a National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI)
- Establishment of a Germany-wide network of competencies (driven by the scientific communities)
- Change of funding policies towards sustainable structures
- Development of new job profiles (Data Librarian, Data Scientist)
- Investment in „minds“ (Staff for development and operation of RDM services)
- Fundamental change of scientific culture
- Initiation of a transition process within the next 15 to 20 years

Resolution of GWK

The joint science conference (GWK) decided to fund a National Research Data Infrastructure. NFDI will be funded with up to 90 Mio Euro per year until 2028, whereof 90% are provided by the federal German government and 10% by the German states. The program starts on 1st of January 2019. (GWK, 16.11.2018)

Tasks of NFDI consortia

- Define common standards
- Develop new methods to evaluate data
- Enable subsequent use of data
- Identify demands for RDM
- Community building in research domain
- Form governance structures

Selection and Evaluation

- Performed by the DFG
- Strictly science-driven process
- Final decision by the Joint Science Conference (GWK)
- Expert Committee, comprising scientists and members of scientific infrastructure facilities, accompany the selection process

Funding

- Three application rounds: 2019, 2020 and 2021
- Funding of up to 30 consortia in total
- About 70 Mio. Euro project costs per year (final funding of 85 Mio., including 22% overhead)
- Between 2 and 5 Mio. Euro funding per consortium, including overhead costs
- Applications for funding period of five years
- Only applications with topical or methodical focus

Funding Criteria

1. Readiness and Relevance of the Consortium

- Embedding of the consortium in the community of interest
- Structural significance to the NFDI and the academic research system
- Capacity to coordinate activities internationally

2. Research Data Management Strategy

- Scientific relevance and quality of existing and planned measures
- Strategy for data use, access, findability and reusability
- Added value achieved through the development of cross-disciplinary metadata standards
- Creation of scientifically reliable and durable services in the consortium

3. Consortium Structure and Viability

- Efficiency and longevity
- Operating model (including moderate user fees where applicable)

NFDI4Microbiota

Common challenges

- Bioinformatical expertise required
- Computational infrastructure required
- Lack of metadata standards
- Reuse of data limited

Vision

Researchers with different scientific questions can easily translate omics data into a deep understanding of microbial species and their interactions.

Mission

NFDI4Microbiota is the central hub and a one-stop shop for the microbiology community for providing access to data, analysis services, data/metadata standards and training in Germany.

Community

Researchers working on omics data of bacterial, archaeal, fungal, viral and/or protozoal samples.

We want to provide ...

Bioinformatics Tools / Databases

(Multi-omics analyses, interaction modeling, semantical enrichment ...)

Computational Infrastructure

(Workflows engines with web interfaces on top of VMs)

Standards

(Standards regarding sampling, processing and metadata, FAIR principles)

Training

(Concepts, good practices and computational skills)

The consortium

Thomas Clavel

Alfred Pühler
Alexander Sczyrba

Jörg Overmann

Peer Bork

Alexander Goesmann

Alice McHardy

Manja Marz

Anke Becher

Ulisses Nunes da Rocha

Konrad Förstner

Workflow engines

Standard development

The BacDive logo is a stylized starburst or flower-like shape composed of various colored segments (green, blue, red, black). Below the logo, the text 'The Bacterial Diversity Metadatabase' is displayed. A search bar contains the text 'species name, culture col. no., sequence no.' and a magnifying glass icon. Below the search bar, it says 'for a comprehensive search use our [Advanced Search](#)'. At the bottom, it says 'Member of:' followed by the logos for de.NBI and elixir.

Databases

Cloud infrastructure

A screenshot of the LIVIVO search portal. The page has a blue header with the LIVIVO logo and a search bar. Below the header, there is a list of search categories including 'Animal Protection', 'Biodiversity', 'Breast Cancer', 'Climate Change', 'Colony Collapse Disorder', 'Crisis Care', 'Dementia', 'Ecosystem Services', 'Food Allergy', 'Glycobiology', 'Hospital Hygiene', 'HPV Vaccination', 'Influenza', 'Interleukin-23', 'Jumping Gene', 'Malaria', 'Microplastics', 'Nanomedicine', 'Nuclear Disaster', 'Nanogenomics', 'Oncogene', 'Organ Donation', 'Organic Farming', 'Particle Resilience', 'Public Health', 'Tissue Impacts', 'Vergins', 'Viral DNA', 'Zoonosis', and 'Zoster'. At the bottom, there is a ZB MED logo.

Discovery Systems

Supporting research societies

Vereinigung für
Allgemeine und
Angewandte
Mikrobiologie

Participants

- Research institutes, services units
- Potentially receive flexible NFDI funds
- Can contribute by
 - Suggesting measures
 - Designing standards
 - Provide data and software
 - Use and promote NFDI4Microbiota within their local research community
 - Join the User Council and/or the Scientific Advisory Board
 - Give general feedback

Participants

Universitätsklinikum
Erlangen

ROBERT KOCH INSTITUT

Organization, governance and interactions

Interacting consortia

- NFDI4Health
- NFDI4BioDiversity
- NFDI4Agri
- GHGA
- DataPLANT
- NFDI4AIRR
- NFDI4RSE

Timeline to submission

Many thanks for your attention

Contact: contact@nfdi4microbiota.de

<https://nfdi4microbiota.de>

@nfdi4microbiota

What are your questions?

Image sources:

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